

tion access feedings alternately with TN1, using male or female GLH adults. For the control, GLH were tested successively on TN1 and IR5492.

Two trials were conducted, using 80 RTV-viruliferous GLH per variety. Three weeks after inoculation, plants were indexed for RTBV and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) by the latex test.

With alternate feeding, GLH transmitted mainly RTBV alone on highly resistant ARC11554, IR5492, and IR74. On moderately resistant IR36 and susceptible TN1, either RTBV + RTSV or RTBV alone was transmitted (see figure). Transmission by GLH decreased with increases in inoculation feeding time.

GLH retained virus infectivity throughout six alternate feedings on ARC11554, IR5492, IR74, IR36, and TN1 and throughout six serial feedings on TN1, but lost infectivity after two successive feedings on IR5492.

Alternate feeding did not demonstrate any effect of GLH feeding on highly resistant varieties and their transmission of the virus in subsequent feedings on susceptible TN1, except for RTBV transmission in highly resistant varieties. □

Infection of RTBV and RTSV in ARC1 1554, IR74, IR36, and IR5492 plants after 6 sequential 4-h inoculation feedings alternately on TN1 (a to d) and in succession in GLH- and RTV-susceptible TN1 and GLH-resistant IR5492 plants (e and f).

Inheritance of resistance to bacterial blight (BB) in rice

Luo Lijun, China National Rice Research Institute; and Zhang Duanpin and Xie Yuefeng, Huazhong Agricultural University, China

Yunnan, one of the centers of origin of *Oryza sativa* L., may also be a center of resistance genes. We screened 96 cultivars from Yunnan for resistance to BB *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*. Traditional cultivar Yunnan Dali was found to be resistant (Table 1).

The mode of inheritance of Yunnan Dali's resistance to a bacterial strain from Jiangling 691, a representative rice and isolate in central China, was studied. We analyzed the F₁, F₂, and F₃ populations from crosses of Yunnan Dali and three other cultivars. With susceptible Guangluai 4, Yunnan Dali

Table 1. Type, origin, and BB resistance reaction of rice cultivars in Yunnan, China. 1986.

Cultivar	Type	Origin	Score	
			1985 ^a	1986 ^b
Yunnan Dali	Japonica	Yunnan	3.3	3.5
IR28	Indica	IRRI	2.0	1.0
Nankeng 15	Japonica	Jiangsu	1.5	1.0
Guangluai 4	Indica	Guangdong	9.0	9.0

^aFor 26 plants. ^bFor 30 plants.

Table 2. Classification of F₁ and F₂ plants for BB from crosses of Yunnan Dali with resistant and susceptible cultivars. Yunnan, China, 1986.

Cross	F ₁ score	F ₂			Xc ²
		R	S	T	
Yunnan Dali/Guangluai 4	8.0	36	394	430	2.935 (1:15)
Yunnan Dali/IR28	1.0	371	103	474	0.089 (49:15)
Yunnan Dali/Nankeng 15	1.0	358	107	464	0.026 (49:15)

resistance is controlled by two recessive genes with overlapping effects (Table 2). It is not allelic with the dominant

genes in IR28 and Nankeng 15 and is not allelic with *xa-5*, *xa-8*, and *xa-9* genes. These are two new genes. □